

ROLE OF INVESTIGATION ON APPLICATION OF AM FUNGI IN THE GRASSLAND ECOSYSTEM FROM BUFFER AREA OF MELGHAT TIGER RESERVE

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Abstract

Arbuscular Mycorrhizal fungi forms a mutualistic relationship with most of the plant species including grass. Its key role to exchange nutrient make each other mutually stable in a adverse condition. The Investigation purpose of this study to find out the Palatability or accountability of AM fungi in the Grassland ecosystem. Purpose of the study is to analyse the AM root colonization and spore population. And, on the basis of that AM fungi increased the phosphorous content, Biomass production, which improves Palatability of grass & indirectly the grazing tendency which help to maintain stable Producer-herbivore life cycle.

Keywords - Arbuscular Mycorrhizal fungi, Palatability or accountability, analyse, life cycle.

Introduction

This study is intent to focus on the symbiotic association between host plant root and mycorrhizal fungi on the Grassland ecosystem from Buffer area of Melghat Tiger Reserve. As the name indicates, Melghat is exactly a meeting place of ghats. It includes succession of hills and valleys with constant and abrupt variations in altitude, aspect and gradient. Melghat forests lies in the satpura range which is usually a dry mixed deciduous type of ecosystem whereas Teak (*Tectona grandis* Linn.) is the most abundant species found in the forests region. The vegetation of forests varies considerably with the compartment which include changes in altitude, rainfall and soil type. All these factors give an ability to harbour a stronger relationship among AM Fungi and host plant.

Mycorrhiza is a mutual relationship occur between host plants and certain group of fungi at the root system, in which fungus get benefitted by gaining its carbon requirements from the photosynthates of the host and the host plant in turn is benefitted by gaining the essential nutrients such as phosphorous, calcium, copper. Arbuscular mycorrhizas (AM) were named according to the structures they occur inside plant cells, called arbuscules. AM Fungi are ubiquitously occur in nature and are important for plant diversity and productivity. It belong to Phylum Glomeromycota. AM Fungi thought to describe an ancient association between plants and fungi, and appears to be evolved with the first land plants. It is one of the most abundant groups of organisms, found in almost all terrestrial ecosystems. It is an obligate symbionts and promote phosphorous uptake also protect plant against various types of stress.

Study Area Context – The study was carried out in the Buffer compartments of Melghat Tiger Reserve which include the Motha, Madki and Lawada villages which is situated at the external part of forests. The only geological formation symbolizes in Melghat is Deccan trap. The soil types vary greatly over hills, Plateaus, slopes and flat areas. The variation is also due to the different conditions of weathering, rainfall within the tract. The texture of soil in in slopy area is clay loam to clay. The PH of the soil is neutral to slightly acidic and mostly suitable for species. Clayey soil occur in the flat areas. It is black in colour, greatly fertile hence seldom carry good forest. Lateritic loam type found in hill tops which red brown in colour. Its red brown colour due to the presence of iron oxides and contains numerous small round stones.

Research Objectives –

Role of AM fungi in Grassland – Palatibility or productivity of grasses depend on the association of AM fungi with the plant.

Effect of AM fungi on root growth of Grass– Fungi are deeply penetrated inside the host plant which make them more efficient for nutrient mobilization from soil.

Study of distribution pattern of AM fungi – To find out abundance of certain type of AM fungal species found in those region and its impact on vegetation.

4.

Role in Plant growth – Due to colonization of AM spores the plant will grow efficiently, increase nutrient uptake and is more able to protect plant against pathogen.

Role during Stress – AM fungi protect plant during stress condition. It lead to release certain chemical and makes the plant stress tolerator.

Review of Literature Steinberg *et al.*, 2007; reported that Arbuscular mycorrhizal (AM) fungi are obligate symbiotic fungi and endosymbionts of a variety of plants within the Angiosperms. It showed AM fungi have three major components: the root itself which provides carbon in the form of sugars to the fungus, fungal structures within cortical cells of plant root that provide contact between fungus and the plant cytoplasm and the extraradical hyphae that aid uptake of nutrients and water.

The evolution of AM fungi can be dated back 460 million years ago from fossil records of the Ordovician age. These records suggest that AM fungi may have played a crucial role in colonisation of most terrestrial plants. (Brundrett, 2002; Redecker *et al.*, 2000; Smith and Read; 1997). The distribution of VAM spores in semiarid zone of Western Ghats of India. Beena *et al.*, (2000) studied the diversity of AM fungi on coastal sand dunes of the West Coast of India. Muthukumar *et al.* (2000)

The comparative study on species diversity of AM fungi in different seasonal areas of South Africa and Namibia. Results revealed that geographical distance and rainfall to a lesser extent, influenced species diversity. A consideration of seasonal changes was also suggested by Dames (1991) when AM fungal species responded differently to soil fertility factors such as pH, moisture, percentage carbon, phosphorus and cations. (Uhlmann *et al.*, 2004)

The study of many mycorrhizal fungi are not host specific and one fungal individual can colonize and interconnect a considerable number of plants. The existence of these so called mycorrhizal networks implies that fungi have the potential to facilitate growth of other plants and distribute resources among plants irrespective of their size, status or identity. In this paper, we explored the significance of mycorrhizal fungal networks for individual plants and for plant communities. (Marcel *et al.*, *Journal of Ecology* 2009, 97, 1139-1150)

The study of mycorrhizal fungi can benefit nursery propagation and production systems. (Fred T. Davies) To explore the diversity of mycorrhizal fungi in the rhizospheric soil of perennial grass species (*Saccharum spontaneum*, *Saccharum bengalense*, *Setaria verticillata*, *Cymbopogon jwarancusa*, and *Typha angustata*). It concluded that, inoculation of mycorrhizal fungi improves the mycorrhizal characteristics of *Cenchrus ciliaris* and its rhizospheric soil and ultimately enhances the growth and physiological parameters of *Cenchrus ciliaris*. (Sumaira Thind *et al.*, 2022)

Material & Method

Sampling & Analysis of Soil - The rhizospheric soil of grasses was collected from the 3 villages of Buffer area of MTR in the the month of February 2023 Amravati District.

Preservation of Soil Sample – The rhizospheric soil was collected in a sterile polythene bags, dried it in a sun and store it at a normal room temperature.

Quantitative & Qualitative estimation of AM fungi - The procedure described by **Gaur & Adholeya (1994)** was used for counting AM fungal spores from sample are as follows –

100gm of soil mixed in a Distilled water in a large beaker. It takes an half an hour to settle this soil. After this, the contents of the beaker was decanted by using descending order of mesh no. 400 (0.037) use it firstly then 300 (0.0053mm) used second time, 200 (0.75mm) for the third and very small size mesh no.100 (0.0150mm). This process was repeated 4-5times. Different methods are use to isolate VAM spores from the soil sample. In present study, the wet sieving and decanting technique (**Gerdeman and Nicolson, 1963**) was used AM spores retained on the sieves were carefully collected into beaker. The remaining spores filtered

with the help of filter paper & spread it on a bigger petri dish. The petri plate was observed under the stereo binocular dissecting microscope. Lines were focused in the field and by moving the petri plates, the spores were counted in every space between the two lines were numbered and the direction set, it was easy to keep track of each spore on the filter paper.

Slide Preparation - Permanent slides were prepared by using PVL (polyvinyl alcohol lactophenol) as a mounted this allows the slides to remain usable for years. Slides along with appropriate photographs requisite taxonomic information (INPM-sheets) .

Observation

The soil sample collected from the four grass species from the Buffer area of MTR under the Motha, Madki & Lawada villages which are *Heteropogon contortus*, *Dichanthium annulatum*, *Themeda quadrivalvis*, *Cynodon dactylon*. The AM accountability was determine on the basis of measuring Ph, Soil texture, Carbon content & AM fungal spore abundance in the certain grass species. The observation table are as follows:

Species name	Area	Texture	ph	Carbon %	No. of Spores
<i>Themeda quadrivalvis</i>	Motha	Clay	7.0	0.25%	13
	Madki	Loamy	6.8	0.28%	18
	Lawada	Slit	6.5	0.39%	4
<i>Heteropogon contortus</i>	Motha	Coarse	6.5	0.38%	14
	Madki	Slit	6.8	0.31%	9
	Lawada	Loamy	7.1	0.40%	13
<i>Dichanthium annulatum</i>	Motha	Fine	7.0	0.35%	15
	Madki	Clay	6.5	0.33%	8
	Lawada	Slit	7.0	0.44%	7
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	Motha	Loamy	7.0	0.28%	11
	Madki	Slit	7.1	0.34%	16
	Lawada	Coarse	7.5	0.42%	12

Result

Rhizospheric soil sample from 12 different sites in Buffer region of MTR of Amravati District where subjected to depict AM fungal spores. All the soil samples from different villages shows different type of spores belonging to different genera. Namely *Acaulospora*, *Glomus*, *Entrophospora*, *Gigaspora*. The collected rhizospheric soil sample exhibited the presence of wide range of spore population. Highest mycorrhizal spores was observed in the rhizospheric soil sample of *Cynodon dactylon* i.e. 39 spores obtained from Melghat Tiger Reserve, where as lowest spore number was observed in rhizospheric soil of *Dicanthium annulatum* i.e. 30 spores obtained from Melghat region. While grass species of *Themeda quadrivalvis* and *Heteropogon contortus* having average number of mycorrhizal spores.

Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi can form relationship not only with plants but with the grasses also. Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi are occur in adventitious roots of grass, specifically in nutrient-poor soils where the plants can rely more heavily on fungal associations to obtain essential nutrients. These associations have significant benefits for the growth and health of the grass. AM fungi can help grasses to obtain nutrients such as phosphorous and nitrogen from the soil, and may also play a role in protecting the plants from diseases and other stresses. The presence of abundance of VAM fungi in the roots can vary depending on several factors, the soil conditions, and the level of colonization in the roots. Therefore, AM fungi certainly present in adventitious roots of grass.

Conclusion-

A survey on the arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) in the rhizosphere of grass and its colonization on the soil were conducted in twelve areas located in several regions of Melghat Tiger Reserve situated in Chikhaldara Taluka, District- Amravati. The objective of the present study to illustrate the palability of grass by the associated arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AM) in the collected soil sample. *Acaulospora* is the dominant genera of AM fungi associated with *Themeda quadrivalvis* having edaphic factor as a concluding factor. *Glomus* is the dominant genera of AM fungi associated with *Heteropogon contortus* having climatic factor is a concluding remark. *Glomus* is the dominant genera of AM fungi associated with *Dicanthium annulatum* having humus as a concluding remark. *Glomus* is the dominant genera of AM fungi associated with *Cynodon dactylon* having concluding factor as a microbial composition.

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